

Involvement in Campus Organization and Student Psychological Well-Being at University for Development Studies, Tamale

Christian Evadzi

*Department of Educational Foundations,
University for Development Studies, Ghana*

Abdul-Razak Mohammed

*Department of Educational Foundations,
University for Development Studies, Ghana*

Abstract

The study assessed the association between involvement in campus-based organization and psychological well-being among students at the Dungu Campus of the University for Development Studies, Tamale. A quantitative cross-sectional survey design was employed. The study population consisted of 5,643 undergraduate students who were members of campus-based organizations, from which a sample of 374 respondents were selected using simple random sampling. Data were collected using adapted psychological well-being questionnaire based on established dimensions of well-being. Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, were computed to summarize the data and One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to examine differences in psychological well-being across levels of organizational involvement. The results revealed a statistically significant difference in psychological well-being based on level of involvement, $F(2, 371) = 195.447, p < .001$. Post-hoc interpretations indicated that students with active involvement reported large effect size manifesting as higher psychological well-being than those with moderate or passive involvement. The study concludes that level of involvement in campus-based organization is positively associated with students' psychological well-being. It is recommended that university authorities and student leadership promote inclusive and structured participation in campus organizations to enhance student engagement and psychological well-being.

Keywords: *Campus-Based Organization, Psychological Well-being, Involvement, University Students, Ghana.*

Suggested citation: Evadzi, C. & Mohammed, A. (2026). Involvement in Campus Organization and Student Psychological Well-Being at University for Development Studies, Tamale. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 4(3), 89-106. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2026.4(3).07

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Introduction

Campus-based organizations are student groups within higher education institutions that promote interpersonal relationships, career development, and extracurricular engagements (Ginosyan et al., 2020). Historically, they emerged to meet students' social and cultural needs and to complement formal academic structures (Buckley & Lee, 2021). Early student initiated groups supported shared interests such as debating and intellectual exchange beyond standardized curricula, nurturing collaboration and student-centred learning (Foley et al., 2024). Over time, these organizations have evolved into platforms that support students' autonomy in intellectual and personal development, particularly in response to perceived limitations of formal academic programmes (Wenoba, 2019). Consequently, they are increasingly recognized for their contribution to students' social and emotional well-being. University students commonly face challenges such as heavy academic workloads, independent learning demands, and time management difficulties, which may contribute to stress and reduced psychological well-being (Seppälä et al., 2020). Research on student well-being has long established links between mental health, academic performance, and social engagement (Baik et al., 2019). In Ghana, these concerns are further intensified by financial constraints, academic pressures, and psychological stressors affecting students' mental health (Dhanabhakym & Sarath, 2023).

University environment presents opportunities but also challenges that call for students adjustment. Again, while exposure to diverse social and cultural contexts can enhance learning, it may also lead to social isolation, particularly among first-year and marginalized students (Morales-Rodríguez et al., 2020). In such contexts, strong social support systems are critical for reducing loneliness and promoting resilience and well-being (Huppert, 2009). Campus-based organizations therefore play an important role in fostering social integration, belonging, and emotional support (Hermon & Hazler, 2022). Empirical studies show that students involved in clubs, sports, leadership, or volunteer activities report lower stress, higher self-esteem, and stronger social relationships compared to non-participants (Anwar et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2024). These activities also support the development of leadership, communication, and coping skills essential for academic and personal success (Panyukova & Panyukov, 2022).

In the Ghanaian higher education context, the expansion of academic programmes and enrollment has increased pressure on students, heightening concerns about psychological well-being. This underscores the importance of informal support systems such as campus-based organizations in complementing institutional student welfare services (Baik et al., 2019; Dhanabhakym & Sarath, 2023). These organizations reflect Ghana's communal values and provide structured platforms for peer support and identity development. Religious groups offer emotional and moral support, academic and professional associations enhance peer learning and career development, while political and leadership organizations foster civic engagement and leadership skills (Hermon & Hazler, 2022; Roothman et al., 2023). Cultural and social groups further support students in maintaining cultural identity while adapting to diverse university environments (Wenoba, 2019; McAuliff et al., 2023). Regardless of these benefits, involvement in campus organization may also present challenges. Students often balance academic responsibilities, financial constraints, and organizational demands, which can lead to stress, burnout, or role conflict, particularly in leadership positions (Seppälä et al., 2020; Soria et al., 2025).

In addition, unequal access to opportunities and gender dynamics may influence the benefits derived from involvement (Anwar et al., 2021). Accordingly, this study

examines the relationship between involvement in campus-based organizations and psychological well-being among the university students, with particular attention to differences based on level of involvement.

Statement of the Problem

Psychological well-being among university students has become an increasingly urgent concern as academic pressures, financial strain, social expectations, and the transition to independent living place significant demands on young adults. Many students experience heightened levels of stress, anxiety, and depression, which can negatively affect their academic performance, interpersonal relationships, and overall quality of life. Although counselling services exist in the universities, utilization is often limited due to stigma and resource constraints, leading students to rely more heavily on peer-based support within campus organizations (Morales-Rodríguez et al., 2020). This highlights the need to understand how both the extent and nature of involvement influence psychological well-being. More so, notwithstanding the growing recognition of student well-being as a critical issue in Ghanaian higher education, empirical research examining the relationship between campus-based organizational involvement and psychological well-being remains limited. Existing studies have largely focused on academic outcomes or general student experiences, with less attention given to the psychological implications of varying levels of involvement in extracurricular contexts (Cheng, 2024; Summerlot et al., 2019). This gap in the literature necessitates further investigation, particularly in relation to how different forms and intensities of participation influence students' well-being. The **objective of the study** is to assess the relationship between students' level of involvement in campus-based organization and their psychological well-being.

Literature Review

Two theories that support the research were reviewed. The social support theory, and self-determination theory. These theories explain how the sense of group membership, involvement and belonging support student psychological well-being.

Social Support Theory

Social Support Theory, originally proposed by Cobb (1976) and later expanded by Cohen and Wills (2019), provides a robust framework for understanding the role of supportive social relationships in promoting psychological well-being. The theory posits that individuals who perceive themselves as cared for, valued, and embedded within a supportive social network are better equipped to cope with stress and manage life challenges (LaCoursiere, 2021; Sarason et al., 2020). It emphasizes that access to meaningful and protective relationships serves as a critical buffer against psychological distress (Hobfoll et al., 2020). Within the context of this study, social support is conceptualized as a key mechanism through which campus-based organizations influence students' psychological well-being. The theory further suggests that social support may function differently across gender, with female students often relying more on emotional and relational support, while male students may derive support through competence-building and activity-based engagement (Meng et al., 2019; Albrecht & Adelman, 2020).

The three primary forms of support, emotional, informational, and instrumental are particularly relevant, as they manifest in campus organizations through peer interaction, mentoring, and academic assistance (Ann, 2019; Nordin, 2022). These

forms of support are associated with reduced stress, enhanced self-esteem, and improved social integration (Cohen & Wills, 2019).

Campus-based organizations at the University for Development Studies serve as important social structures through which students access these supportive networks. However, the theory also acknowledges that not all forms of social support are beneficial, as some may foster dependency or limit autonomy (Ganster & Victor, 2019). Despite this limitation, Social Support Theory remains a valuable framework for examining how varying levels of organizational involvement contribute to students' psychological well-being.

Self-Determination Theory

Deci and Ryan (1985) have proposed the Self-determination Theory (SDT) as a motivational approach to psychological well-being. According to the theory, human beings have three basic psychological needs (BPNs): autonomy, competence and relatedness; if BPNs are satisfied then optimal functioning is possible and well-being is promoted (Guay, 2022). And when they are fulfilled, people feel intrinsically motivated, that they are developing themselves and that their welfare is improving. By contrast, when these needs are frustrated, people can feel frustration, stress and lower psychological well-being (Diefendorff et al., 2022; Ryan & Deci, 2020).

A central tenet of SDT is that social contexts (e.g., schools, organizations) can aid or thwart the satisfaction of these needs (Deci et al., 2021). This proposition is closely associated with the objective of this study, which is to investigate whether and how involvement in campus organization is associated with psychological well-being. Active bodily and meaningful involvement is believed to meet the students need for relatedness with friends, competence through learning new skills and the autonomy by having part in decision-making (Suoranta 2010). Passive or partial involvement is likely to fail to meet these needs and bear fewer psychological fruits (Scarlett, 2024). The key constructs of autonomy, competence, and relatedness are particularly relevant to our study. Autonomy is a sense of choice, and control over one's actions; competence is an experience of mastery and effectiveness; and relatedness is the feeling of being connected to others (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2020). Within organizational citizenship behaviour, students in leadership roles or who are involved in decision-making often report experience high levels of autonomy and competence, while group membership can provide a sense of relatedness (Martela, 2020).

Self-determination theory (Ryan and Deci, 2000) is important to the current study because it connects organization-based participation with students' motivational and emotional experiences. Not only does it account for whether well-being benefits are realized or not, but it also explains how different levels of involvement produce varying outcomes (Deci & Ryan, 2020; Gagné & Deci; in press). A limitation of the theory is that it assumes that all students have a need for autonomy, competence, and relatedness to an equal extent and does not accommodate different cultures with differing motivating focuses (Scarlett 2024). Nevertheless, due to its focus on fundamental human needs it is a valuable approach to the analysis of organizational participation from psychological point of view. Collectively, these theories explain why more engagement is generally associated with healthier psychological outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual framework showing the influence of campus-based organizations on Psychological well-being of students

The study was guided by a conceptual framework examining the influence of campus-based organizations on students' psychological well-being at the University for Development Studies, Tamale. The model posits that the level of involvement in campus-based organizations (independent variable) directly influences psychological well-being (dependent variable). While low participation may limit access to social support and identity development, excessive involvement may contribute to role strain and stress.

Empirical Review

Campus-Based Organizations

Campus-based organizations are formal student groups formed around shared academic, cultural, religious, political, or recreational interests (Jones et al., 2022). They provide structured opportunities for student engagement, peer interaction, and leadership development and are widely recognized as integral to holistic university education (Glass & Gesing, 2020). According to Austin (1999), student involvement model, co-curricular participation significantly shapes students' academic and social experiences by fostering belonging, easing adjustment, and enhancing networking and engagement within university life (Cheng, 2024). Beyond their developmental role, these organizations function as social systems that influence students' values, skills, and emotional experiences (McAuliff et al., 2023). This study therefore considers campus organizations as potential determinants of students' psychological well-being, with effects likely to vary level of involvement.

Psychological Well-Being

Psychological well-being refers to positive psychological functioning, including life satisfaction, self-acceptance, and quality interpersonal relationships, beyond the absence of mental illness (Farozin et al., 2022). Ryff's (1989) multidimensional model conceptualizes well-being through six domains: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self-acceptance (Prachurjya & Nisanth, 2024). In university contexts, where students face academic, financial, and social pressures, psychological well-being is particularly relevant. Campus-based organizations may support well-being by providing social support, identity development, and opportunities for personal growth, although outcomes may vary depending on the nature of engagement (Roothman et al., 2023). Thus, psychological well-being is conceptualized in this study as a key outcome potentially shaped by organizational involvement.

Level of Involvement

There are varying degrees of student involvement in campus organizations, ranging from passive membership to active leadership roles (Berti et al., 2023). Prior research suggests that higher levels of engagement are associated with increased satisfaction, leadership development, and personal growth (Mustaqim & Wahjoedi, 2024). However, the relationship is not linear, as excessive involvement may lead to stress and role conflict, while minimal participation may limit access to social and developmental benefits (Soria et al., 2025). This suggests an optimal level of engagement may be most beneficial for psychological outcomes. Empirical studies generally support a positive association between engagement in structured groups and psychological well-being. For example, Carton and Goodboy (2019) found that higher interaction levels among students were associated with better psychological health, although their focus was limited to classroom settings. Similarly, Fox et al. (2022) reported that higher participation in organizational settings improved well-being outcomes, though their evidence was drawn primarily from workplace contexts. Overall, existing research highlights a gap in understanding how varying intensities of student organizational involvement influence psychological well-being in university settings.

In sum, the literature indicates a consistent association between involvement in campus-based organizations and psychological well-being. Theoretical and empirical evidence suggests that involvement can enhance well-being through social support, identity formation, and skill development, while also presenting risks such as stress and role strain at higher levels of engagement. Campus organizations are conceptualized as structured environments that facilitate social and developmental experiences, while psychological well-being is understood as a multidimensional construct encompassing autonomy, purpose, self-acceptance, and relatedness. Overall, the literature underscores the importance of examining how contextual and individual factors particularly level of participation, gender, and organizational type, shape the relationship between organizational involvement and psychological well-being

Methods

A quantitative cross-sectional survey design was employed to examine the relationship between involvement in campus-based organizations and psychological well-being among students at the University for Development Studies (UDS), Dungu Campus. Data were collected at a single point in time to assess associations among study variables. While appropriate for identifying relationships in a natural university setting, the design does not permit causal inference. Population The target population comprised undergraduate students at UDS, Dungu Campus who were members of campus-based organizations, including academic, religious, political, cultural, and recreational groups. The accessible population was 5,643 students drawn from 50 recognized student organizations. Students who are not members of any campus-based organization were excluded from the study. The sample size of 374 was determined using Yamane's (1967) formula for finite populations at a 5% margin of error. It provides a simplified approach for estimating sample size in survey research:

The formula is expressed as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad (1)$$

Where n = required sample size, N = population size (5,643), and e = margin of error (0.05 at a 95% confidence level). Substituting these values yielded a sample size of approximately 374 respondents.

A simple random sampling technique was employed to select participants from the target population of students involved in campus-based organizations at the University for Development Studies. This probability sampling method ensured that each individual had an equal and independent chance of selection, thereby minimizing selection bias and enhancing the representativeness and generalizability of the findings.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire adapted from Ryff's (1989) Psychological Well-Being Scale. The instrument comprised two sections: demographic information (e.g., gender, age, year of study, organization type) and psychological well-being items. Psychological well-being was measured on a 6-point Likert type scale (1 = strongly disagree to 6 = strongly agree), covering six dimensions: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. Additional items assessed level of organizational involvement. Both positively and negatively worded items were included, with reverse coding applied where appropriate.

Content and face validity were established through expert review by supervisors and specialists in educational psychology, leading to refinement of item clarity and relevance. Construct validity was supported through adaptation of Ryff's established model. A pilot study with 40 students from Tamale Technical University confirmed instrument clarity. Internal consistency reliability was high (Cronbach's $\alpha = .89$), indicating strong measurement reliability.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of UDS. Permission was secured from organizational leaders before data collection. Participants were selected using proportional allocation across organizations and informed about the study purpose, voluntary participation, and confidentiality were established. Questionnaires were administered in person during meetings and arranged sessions which were completed within 20–30 minutes averagely. Completed instruments were checked for completeness and collected over a two-week period. Ethical principles of voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality, and anonymity were strictly observed. No identifying information was collected, and data were stored securely in cabinets under locked. Results were reported in aggregate form. Proper acknowledgment was given for the use of Ryff's (1989) scale.

Data were coded, cleaned, and analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, and standard deviations) and one-way ANOVA at a 0.05 significance level. ANOVA was used to test differences in psychological well-being across levels of participation and types of campus organizations. Where significant effects were found, Tukey post hoc tests were conducted to identify group differences.

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 presents the gender distribution of the study respondents. Of the total 374 participants, 53% ($n = 200$) were males, while 47% ($n = 174$) were female. This relatively balanced representation ensures that findings can be meaningfully interpreted across gender groups within the sample.

Table 1. Gender Distribution of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	200	53
Female	174	47
Total	374	100

Source: Field Data, 2026

Table 2. Age Distribution of Respondents

Age group	Frequency	Percentage %
Under 20	95	25
20 – 24	108	29
25 – 29	81	22
30 – Above	90	24
Total	374	100

Source: Field Data, 2026

Table 2 displays the age distribution of respondents. The largest group of participants was aged 20 to 24 years ($n = 108$), followed by those aged 30 and above ($n = 90$), under 20 years ($n = 95$), and 25 to 29 years ($n = 82$). This distribution indicates a predominantly young adult sample with diverse age representation across typical university student age ranges.

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents by Year of Study

Level	Frequency	Percentage %
200	121	32.4
300	107	28.6
400	146	39
Total	374	100

Source: Field Data, 2026

Table 3 shows that fourth year students were the highest proportion of respondents (146 students, 39.0%), and those of Level 200 constituted second largest group (121 students, 32.4%). Also, 107 students were from Level 300 (28.6%); the least percentage composition.

Table 4. Distribution of Respondents by Type of Campus-based Organization

Organization type	Frequency (n)	Percentage %
Social/Ethnic	80	21.3
Academic	76	20.3
Political	75	20.1
Sports/recreation	75	20.1
Religious	68	18.2
Total	374	100

Source: Field Data, 2026

Table 4 presents the distribution of respondents across different types of campus-based organizations. Social-ethnic-cultural groups accounted for the highest participation (21.3%, n = 80), closely followed by academic organizations (20.3%, n = 76). Political and sports & recreation organizations each comprised 20.1% of the sample (n = 75 for each), while religious organizations had the lowest representation (18.2%, n = 68). These findings indicate a relatively balanced involvement of students across various types of campus organizations, reflecting heterogeneity in organizational participation within the sample.

Table 5. Distribution of Respondents by Membership Duration in Campus-based Organization

Membership Duration	Frequency(n)	Percentage %
Less than 1 year	75	20.1
1 year	98	26.2
2 years	51	13.6
3 years	70	18.7
4 years	80	21.4
Total	374	100.0

Source: Field Data, 2026

As shown in Table 5, students with one year of membership constituted the largest group (n = 98, 26.2%), followed by those with four years of membership (n = 80, 21.4%). Participants with less than one year of membership accounted for 75 respondents (20.1%), while those with three years of membership represented 70 respondents (18.7%). The smallest group comprised students with two years of membership (n = 51, 13.6%). Overall, the distribution indicates representation of both relatively new members and long-term participants in campus-based organizations.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics of Students' Psychological Well-Being

Construct	N	M	SD
Autonomy			
I am not afraid to voice my opinions, even when they are in opposition to the opinions of most people	374	3.02	0.841
I have confidence in my own opinions, even if they are different from the way most other people think	374	2.96	00.801
I judge myself by what I think is important, not by the values of what others think is important	374	3.00	0.873
I am not easily influenced by others	374	2.95	0.833
I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions R	374	2.96	0.875
Environmental Mastery			
In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live	374	3.02	0.868
I am good at managing the responsibilities of daily life	374	2.97	0.836
I often feel overwhelmed by my responsibilities R	374	3.03	0.795
I have difficulty arranging my life in a way that is satisfying to me R	374	2.97	0.917
I am quite good at managing many responsibilities of my daily life	374	2.95	0.854
Personal Growth			
I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how I think about myself and the world	374	2.95	0.842
I gave up trying to make big improvements or changes in my life a long time ago R	374	3.01	0.866

For me life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth	374	3.00	0.838
I am not interested in activities that will expand my horizons	374	3.06	0.872
I have the sense that I have developed a lot as a person over time	374	3.02	0.912
Relations with Others			
Most people see me as loving and affectionate	374	3.01	0.883
Maintaining close relationships has been difficult and frustrating for me R	374	2.98	0.874
I often feel lonely because I have few close friends with whom to share my concerns R	374	2.94	0.878
I enjoy personal and mutual conversations with family members or friends	374	3.01	0.846
Purpose in Life			
I feel good when I think of what I have done in the past and what I plan to do in the future	374	2.95	0.789
I live life one day at a time and do not really think about the future R	374	3.02	0.858
I tend to focus on the present because the future nearly always brings me problems R	374	2.99	0.880
Self-Acceptance			
When I look at the story of my life, I am pleased with how things have turned out	374	3.00	0.844
In general I feel confident and positive about myself	374	2.94	0.842
I feel like many of the people I know have gotten more out of life than I have R	374	3.01	0.885
Mean of means		2.99	

Source: Field Data, 2026

Descriptive statistics for the six dimensions of psychological well-being (autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self-acceptance) are presented in Table 6. Median scores were generally centered at the midpoint, indicating moderate well-being, with an overall mean of 2.99. Across all dimensions, item means clustered around the scale midpoint (approximately 2.94–3.06), reflecting moderate levels of independence, life management, personal growth, interpersonal relationships, goal orientation, and self-acceptance.

Reverse-coded items showed comparable mid-range values, suggesting balanced tendencies within each domain. Overall, participants demonstrated moderate psychological well-being across all six dimensions.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics of Students' Level of Participation in Campus based Organizations

Level of Participation	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Low/Passive	56	15.0	15.0	15.0
Moderate	270	72.2	72.2	87.2
High/Active	48	12.8	12.8	100.0
Total	374	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Data, 2026

The distribution of students' levels of participation in campus-based organizations is presented in Table 7. The findings indicate that the majority of participants (72.2%) reported a moderate level of involvement in campus organizations.

This was followed by a smaller proportion of students (15.0%) who exhibited low or passive participation. In contrast, only 12.8% of the respondents were classified as having a high or active level of participation. These results suggest that while most students engage in campus-based organizations to a moderate extent, relatively few demonstrate a high level of active involvement. This pattern highlights a disparity in the intensity of student participation, with active engagement being comparatively limited among the study population

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics of Psychological Well-being Based on Level of Participation in Campus-Based Organizations

Level of Part	N	M	SD	SE	95% CI	
					LB	UB
Low/Passive	56	57.04	8.180	1.093	54.85	59.23
Moderate	270	74.65	10.422	.634	73.40	75.90
High/Active	48	95.56	8.649	1.248	93.05	98.07
Total	374	74.70	14.159	.732	73.26	76.13

Source: Field Data, 2026

The distribution of students' levels of participation in campus-based organizations is presented in Table 8. The findings indicate that the majority of participants (72.2%) reported a moderate level of involvement in campus organizations. This was followed by a smaller proportion of students (15.0%) who exhibited low or passive participation. In contrast, only 12.8% of the respondents were classified as having a high or active level of participation.

These results suggest that while most students engage in campus-based organizations to a moderate extent, relatively few demonstrate a high level of active involvement. This pattern highlights a disparity in the intensity of student participation, with active engagement being comparatively limited among the study population

Table 9. ANOVA Summary of Psychological Well-being Based on Level of Participation in Campus-Based Organizations

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	38365.936	2	19182.968	195.447	< 0.001
Within Groups	36413.315	371	98.149		
Total	74779.251	373			

Source: Field Data, 2026

Table 9 demonstrates that students' psychological well-being varies significantly by their level of involvement in campus organizations. With between-group differences exceeding within-group differences and a p-value < .001, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that participation meaningfully influences students' mental health.

Table 10. Post Hoc Comparison of Psychological Well-being across Level of Participation (Tukey HSD)

(I) Level of Part	(J) Level of Part	MD (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Low/Passive	Moderate	-17.612*	1.455	< 0.001
	High/Active	-38.527*	1.949	< 0.001
Moderate	Low/Passive	17.612*	1.455	< 0.001
	High/Active	-20.914*	1.552	< 0.001
High/Active	Low/Passive	38.527*	1.949	< 0.001
	Moderate	20.914*	1.552	< 0.001

Source: Field Data, 2026

Following the significant omnibus ANOVA, post hoc comparisons were conducted using the Tukey Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test to determine which levels of participation differed significantly in psychological well-being. The results, presented in Table 10, indicated that all pairwise comparisons were statistically significant. Specifically, students with moderate participation reported significantly higher levels of psychological well-being compared to those with low or passive participation (M difference = 17.61, SE = 1.46, $p < .001$).

Similarly, students with high or active participation demonstrated significantly greater psychological well-being than those with low or passive participation (M difference = 38.53, SE = 1.95, $p < .001$). Furthermore, students who were highly active participants exhibited significantly higher psychological well-being scores than those with moderate participation (M difference = 20.91, SE = 1.55, $p < .001$). Overall, these findings suggest a clear and consistent pattern in which psychological well-being increases as the level of participation in campus-based organizations rises. The fact that all pairwise comparisons were statistically significant underscores the strength of this relationship.

Discussion

The results of the study indicated that positive differentiation had an extremely significant difference in psychological well-being among students regarding their level of involvement in campus-based organizations, $F(2, 371) = 195.447$, $p < .001$. This finding indicates that students who are highly involved in campus-based groups experience more positive psychological effects, with an increasing level of involvement associated with better outcomes. This conclusion is well-aligned with extant empirical work that highlights the benefits of active involvement in structured social and academic settings. For example, involvement was found to have a positive relationship with mental well-being in college students (Carton and Goodboy 2019), highlighting the role that more active community engagement has for one's well-being. Similarly, Kilgo et al. (2020) longitudinally found that higher intensity participation in the campus life was a robust predictor for increased well-being. The current study supports these results by demonstrating that students who have more intensive involvement in campus organizations display significantly better psychological well-being than those with moderate and low levels of engagement.

Further, these findings are consistent with Knifsend's (2020) argument that level of involvement is an important predictor of psychological outcomes, although effects may differ by context. Although Knifsend highlighted variation according to type of participation and individual differences, our findings expand on these results by documenting the large differences in well-being across distinct levels of involvement

empirically, legitimating its contention that just belonging is not enough, engaged and ongoing participation is essential for positive mental health outcomes. Outside the student environment, research on organizational and social participation also confirms these findings. Fox et al. (2022) supported the view that increased involvement in (structured) group organization format significantly improved several dimensions of psychological well-being, whilst Sharifian and Grün (2019) showed that higher frequency of social participation predicted better psychological well-being across the life course. While these studies were conducted in non-student samples, the findings support the idea that active participation in ordered social collectives promotes psychological resilience and well-being, a principle which is consistent with what we have found with university students. Furthermore, Mustaqim and Wahjoedi (2014) also found a statistically higher level of psychological well-being among students who actively engaged with campus organizations, although participation was simply dichotomized in their study. This study extends this line of research by using a more precise classification of the degree to which participation has occurred, providing insight into the extent to which graduated levels of participation in embedded civic life lead to varying psychological responses. This differentiated perspective fills gaps that have been found in earlier research, which has portrayed participation as a dichotomous phenomenon and neglected the third dimension: intensity.

In addition, observations of Lee et al. (2020) on active versus passive engagement in campus-related communities are consistent to emphasize the quality and degree of engagement. While they studied digital engagement, the same principle applies: Active participation creates a stronger mental reward than passive affiliation. This convergence of findings supports the view that intensity of involvement, in both actual organizations and virtual communities is important to well-being. The findings of this study provide compelling evidence that students' psychological well-being improves progressively with higher levels of participation in campus-based organizations. This underscores the importance of encouraging not only student membership but also meaningful and active engagement within campus organizations. From a practical standpoint, university administrators and student leaders should prioritize strategies that facilitate deeper involvement, such as leadership opportunities, structured activities, and inclusive participation frameworks, to enhance students' psychological well-being.

The findings of this study provide strong empirical evidence that students' psychological well-being differs significantly based on their level of participation in campus-based organizations. The results consistently demonstrated that students with higher levels of involvement reported significantly greater psychological well-being compared to those with moderate or low participation. Specifically, the one-way ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference across participation levels, while post hoc analyses confirmed that all pairwise group differences were significant. This pattern indicates a clear, positive relationship between the intensity of organizational involvement and psychological well-being. Furthermore, descriptive findings showed that although the majority of students engaged at a moderate level, those who were actively involved exhibited the highest well-being scores, whereas students with passive participation reported the lowest. This trend underscores the importance of not only participation itself but also the depth and quality of engagement in influencing mental health outcomes. The results align with theoretical perspectives such as Social Support Theory and Self-Determination Theory, which emphasize the role of social connectedness, autonomy, competence, and relatedness in promoting well-being.

Conclusion

Students' psychological well-being differed significantly by level of participation in campus organizations, with higher involvement associated with greater well-being. A one-way ANOVA showed a significant effect, $F(2, 371) = 195.45$, $p < .001$, and post hoc tests confirmed differences across all groups. Although most students reported moderate participation, actively involved students had the highest well-being, while passive participants had the lowest, highlighting the importance of engagement depth. Consistent with Social Support Theory and Self-Determination Theory, the findings indicate that active, meaningful involvement enhances well-being, underscoring the need for universities to promote sustained and inclusive participation.

References

- Ab Ghani, S., Awang, M. M., Ajit, G., & Rani, M. A. M. (2020). Participation in co-curriculum activities and students' leadership skills. *Journal of Southwest Jiaotong University*, 55(4), 48. <https://doi.org/10.35741/issn.0258-2724.55.4.48>
- Abduel, M., & Magingila, K. (2023). Integrity and confidentiality of data protection on consumers' privacy in Tanzania: A case study of TCRA. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 11(03), 4770–4775. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijserm/v11i03.em11>
- Albrecht, T. L., & Adelman, M. B. (2020). Social support and health communication. In T. L. Thompson, R. Parrott, & J. F. Nussbaum (Eds.), *Handbook of health communication* (2nd ed., pp. 303–326). Routledge.
- Ann, M. (1989). Social support: Theory, research, and intervention. *Choice Reviews Online*, 26(08), 26-4781. <https://doi.org/10.5860/CHOICE.26-4781>
- Anwar, Z., Aryani, T., Mawardani, G. A., Sudirman, F., Amaly, I. C., & Yanti, H. (2021). Detox mind: An innovation of Islamic based learning as a psychological well-being intervention in students active in organizations in East Java. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 10(12), 80–84. <https://doi.org/10.21275/SR21805094842>
- Astin, A. W. (1999). Student involvement: A developmental theory for higher education. *Journal of College Student Development*, 40(5), 518–529.
- Baik, C., Larcombe, W., & Brooker, A. (2019). How universities can enhance student mental wellbeing: The student perspective. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 38(4), 674–687. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2019.1576596>
- Berti, S., Grazia, V., & Molinari, L. (2023). Active student participation in whole-school interventions in secondary school: A systematic literature review. *Educational Psychology Review*, 35, Article 52. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-023-09773-x>
- Buckley, P., & Lee, P. (2021). The impact of extra-curricular activity on the student experience. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 22(1), 37–48. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787418808988>
- Carton, S. T., & Goodboy, A. K. (2015). College students' psychological well-being and interaction involvement in class. *Communication Research Reports*, 32(2), 180–184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08824096.2015.1016145>

- Cheng, D. X. (2004). Students' sense of campus community: What it means, and what to do about it. *NASPA Journal*, 41(2), 216–234. <https://doi.org/10.2202/1949-6605.1331>
- Cobb, S. (1976). Social support as a moderator of life stress. *Psychosomatic Medicine*, 38(5), 300–314. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00006842-197609000-00003>
- Cohen, S., & Wills, T. A. (1985). Stress, social support, and the buffering hypothesis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 98(2), 310–357. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.98.2.310>
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The “what” and “why” of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- Deci, E. L., Vallerand, R. J., Pelletier, L. G., & Ryan, R. M. (1991). Motivation and education: The self-determination perspective. *Educational Psychologist*, 26(3–4), 325–346. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.1991.9653137>
- Dhanabhakyaam, M., & Sarath, M. (2023). Psychological wellbeing: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology*, 603–607. <https://doi.org/10.48175/IJARSC-8345>
- Diefendorff, J. M., Houliort, N., Vallerand, R. J., & Krantz, D. (2022). Emphasizing the self in organizational research on self-determination theory. In D. L. Ferris & R. E. Sedikides (Eds.), *The self at work* (1st ed., pp. 145–171). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315626543-7>
- Evadzi, C. (2026). Gender and campus-based organization type as determinants of students' psychological wellbeing at the University for Development Studies. *International Journal of Social Science Research and Review*, 9(3), 504–521. <https://doi.org/10.47814/ijssrr.v9i3.3302>
- Farozin, M., Purnama, D. S., Astuti, B., Prasetya, A. B., & Nurbaiti, A. T. (2022). College students' psychological well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic: An investigation based on students' gender and education level. *Jurnal Kajian Bimbingan Dan Konseling*, 7(1), 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.17977/um001v7i12022p20-28>
- Foley, C., Darcy, S., Hergesell, A., Almond, B., McDonald, M., & Brett, E. (2024). University-based sport and social clubs and their contribution to the development of graduate attributes. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 25(3), 337–354. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14697874221127692>
- Fox, J., et al. (2022). Organizational participation and employee well-being: A systematic review. *Work & Stress*, 36(3), 200–218. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678373.2021.1891887>
- Gagné, M., & Deci, E. L. (2005). Self-determination theory and work motivation. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 26(4), 331–362. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.322>
- Ganster, D. C., & Victor, B. (1988). The impact of social support on mental and physical health. *British Journal of Medical Psychology*, 61(1), 17–36. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8341.1988.tb02763.x>
- Ginosyan, H., Tuzlukova, V., & Ahmed, F. (2020). Student organizations and academic development. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 74(3), 310–325. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hequ.12255>

- Glass, C., & Gesing, P. (2020). Co-curricular engagement in universities. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 43(2), 145–160. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2020.1864193>
- Guay, F. (2022). Applying self-determination theory to education: Regulation types, psychological needs, and autonomy-supporting behaviors. *Canadian Journal of School Psychology*, 37(1), 75–92. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08295735211055355>
- Hagger, M., & Chatzisarantis, N. (2008). Self-determination theory and the psychology of exercise. *International Review of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 1(1), 79–103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17509840701827437>
- Hermon, D. A., & Hazler, R. J. (1999). Adherence to a wellness model and perceptions of psychological well-being. *Journal of Counseling & Development*, 77(3), 339–343. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1556-6676.1999.tb02457.x>
- Hobfoll, S. E., Freedy, J., Lane, C., & Geller, P. (1990). Conservation of social resources: Social support resource theory. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 7(4), 465–478. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265407590074004>
- Huppert, F. A. (2009). Psychological well-being: Evidence and policy implications. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 364(1534), 373–388. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2008.0211>
- Jones, A., Smith, B., & Lee, C. (2022). University clubs and student engagement. *Journal of Student Affairs Research and Practice*, 59(2), 100–115.
- Kilgo, C. A., Mollet, A. L., & Pascarella, E. T. (2016). The estimated effects of college student involvement on psychological well-being. *Journal of College Student Development*, 57(8), 1043–1049. <https://doi.org/10.1353/csd.2016.0098>
- Knifsend, C. A. (2020). Extracurricular participation, collective self-esteem, and academic outcomes among college students. *Psi Chi Journal of Psychological Research*, 25(4), 335–343. <https://doi.org/10.24839/2325-7342.JN25.4.335>
- Koo, K. K. (2021). Am I welcome here? Campus climate and psychological well-being among students of color. *Journal of Student Affairs Research and Practice*, 58(2), 196–213. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19496591.2020.1853557>
- LaCoursiere, S. P. (2001). A theory of online social support. *Advances in Nursing Science*, 24(1), 60–77. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00012272-200109000-00008>
- Lee, D., Ng, P. M. L., & Bogomolova, S. (2020). The impact of university brand identification and eWOM behaviour on students' psychological well-being: A multi-group analysis among active and passive social media users. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 36(3–4), 384–403. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0267257X.2019.1702082>
- Martela, F. (2020). Self-determination theory. In B. J. Carducci, C. S. Nave, & C. S. Nave (Eds.), *The Wiley encyclopedia of personality and individual differences* (pp. 369–373). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118970843.ch61>
- McAuliff, K. E., Williams, S. M., & Ferrari, J. R. (2013). Social justice and the university community: Does campus involvement make a difference? *Journal of Prevention & Intervention in the Community*, 41(4), 244–254. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10852352.2013.818486>
- Meng, J., Martinez, L., Holmstrom, A., Chung, M., & Cox, J. (2017). Research on social networking sites and social support from 2004 to 2015: A narrative review and

directions for future research. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 20(1), 44–51. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2016.0325>

Morales-Rodríguez, F. M., Espigares-López, I., Brown, T., & Pérez-Mármol, J. M. (2020). The relationship between psychological well-being and psychosocial factors in university students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(13), 4778. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134778>

Mustaqim, G. P., & Wahjoedi, T. (2024). Effectiveness of student participation in campus organizations. *INCOME: Innovation of Economics and Management*, 3(3), 29–35. <https://doi.org/10.32764/income.v3i3.5034>

Nordin, M. (2022). Social support: Health benefits from social relations. In *Supporting sleep: The importance of social relations at work* (pp. 13–19). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137437853_2

O’Grady, E. (2016). Research as a respectful practice: An exploration of the practice of respect in qualitative research. *Qualitative Research in Education*, 5(3), 229–251. <https://doi.org/10.17583/qre.2016.2018>

Panyukova, Y. G., & Panyukov, A. I. (2022). Organization of school educational environment as a factor of students’ psychological well-being: Review of foreign studies. *Journal of Modern Foreign Psychology*, 11(3), 49–60. <https://doi.org/10.17759/jmfp.2022110305>

Prachurjya, B., & Nisanth, P. (2024). A study on psychological well-being of secondary students in relation to gender and locality. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Modern Science and Technology*, 3(4), 11–19.

Roothman, B., Kirsten, D. K., & Wissing, M. P. (2003). Gender differences in aspects of psychological well-being. *South African Journal of Psychology*, 33(4), 212–218. <https://doi.org/10.1177/008124630303300403>

Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2020). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory perspective: Definitions, theory, practices, and future directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, 101860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101860>

Ryff, C. D. (1989). Happiness is everything, or is it? Explorations on the meaning of psychological well-being. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 57(6), 1069–1081. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.57.6.1069>

Sarason, I. G., Levine, H. M., Basham, R. B., & Sarason, B. R. (1983). Assessing social support: The social support questionnaire. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 44(1), 127–139. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.44.1.127>

Scarlett, M. (2024). Cultural limitations of self-determination theory. *Cross-Cultural Psychology Review*, 10(1), 22–38.

Seppälä, E. M., Bradley, C., Moeller, J., Harouni, L., Nandamudi, D., & Brackett, M. A. (2020). Promoting mental health and psychological thriving in university students: A randomized controlled trial of three well-being interventions. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 11, 590. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00590>

Sharifian, N., & Grünh, D. (2019). The differential impact of social participation and social support on psychological well-being: Evidence from the Wisconsin longitudinal study. *The International Journal of Aging and Human Development*, 88(2), 107–126. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0091415018757213>

- Song, Z. (2024). Personal growth and well-being among university students: A comprehensive analysis. *Journal of Education in Black Sea Region*, 9(2), 39–47. <https://doi.org/10.31578/jebs.v9i2.316>
- Summerlot, J., Green, S., & Parker, D. (2013). Student veterans organizations. In R. Ackerman & D. DiRamio (Eds.), *Creating a veteran-friendly campus: Strategies for transition and success* (pp. 71–80). Jossey-Bass.
- Suoranta, J. (2010). Participatory learning and autonomy. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 42(2), 200–215. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-5812.2008.00480.x>
- Wenoba, M. (2019). Student autonomy in African universities. *African Journal of Higher Education*, 7(1), 55–70.
- Wu, Y., Wu, D., & Wang, Y. (2024). Enhancement of international students' psychological well-being and social integration through peer-to-peer support networks. *International Education Forum*, 2(1), 41–45. <https://doi.org/10.26689/ief.v2i1.6654>

